

ECHO:

Expanding Concept and Methodology for Human Past Studies in the Eastern
Baltic Countries

Grant Agreement no 101159883

Deliverable 2.3 - Guidelines and Protocols on setting up and running a clean lab for working with highly degraded bioarchaeological materials and sensitive biomolecules

WP2 – Enriching Methodological Toolbox

Due date of deliverable: 31.01.2025

Dissemination level: Public

Start date of project: 01.09.2024

Duration: 36 months

Lead beneficiary for this deliverable: UTARTU

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Executive Summary

This document provides comprehensive guidelines for establishing and operating a clean laboratory dedicated to working with highly degraded bioarchaeological materials and sensitive biomolecules. The guidelines are part of the ECHO project, under the Work Package 2 (WP2) – Enriching Methodological Toolbox, and covers the following aspects:

- The objectives and core principles of the Ancient DNA Facilities
- Description of laboratory design, environmental and access control
- Overview of the workflow and protocols
- Guidelines on personnel training before granting access to the Ancient DNA Facilities
- Means of quality assurance and guidelines on laboratory work documentation
- Plans for long-term infrastructure maintenance and policy updates

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.Introduction and Objectives	4
2.Core Principles	4
3.Physical Lab Design	5
4.Workflow and Protocols.....	8
5.Personnel Training.....	11
6.Quality Assurance	11
7.Long-Term Maintenance and Updates.....	12
8. Appendices and Resources.....	13

1. Introduction and Objectives

The Ancient DNA Facility* (referred to as the Laboratory in this document) is part of the Core Facilities of the Institute of Genomics, University of Tartu (<https://genomics.ut.ee/en>). It has the capacity to generate ancient DNA (aDNA) sequences from various highly degraded bioarchaeological sources. The three main directions of the Laboratory activities are:

1. Research
 - DNA extraction and sequence generation from various ancient sources such as archaeological human and animal remains, materials generated or used by humans (e. g. birch tar) and environmental samples (e. g. sediments)
 - Palaeoproteomics (extraction of proteins from bioarchaeological material). Protocols and workflows of palaeoproteomics are currently under development.
2. Service
 - aDNA extraction and sequencing from a range of bioarchaeological materials and primary sequence analysis for human aDNA.
3. Teaching
 - We provide training for our students and research partners on aDNA extraction and analysis.

* The laboratory was established with financial support from Archimedes Foundation, EU Regional Development Fund, project no 2014-2020.4.01.16-0030

2. Core Principles

The Core principles of the Laboratory are to 1) prevent sample contamination; 2) ensure sample integrity; 3) follow ethical standards. Below we summarise briefly how these principles are addressed:

1. Contamination prevention is ensured by the physical design, environmental and access control (ISO standards 5 and 7), specialized equipment and wet-lab protocols. Please, see chapters 3. and 4. for more details.

2. To ensure sample integrity we adhere to a rule of minimal possible destruction of the objects while maximising their informative value.
3. To ensure ethical standards, we follow the best practices of 1) dignified treatment of human/animal remains; 2) respect for and protection of cultural heritage and 3) the long-term preservation of future research opportunities. While working with various materials, including the ones from deceased individuals, we follow the Code of Ethics of Estonian archaeologists, Estonian Heritage Act (<https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/27815>) and European Convention for the Protection of the Archaeological Heritage (<https://rm.coe.int/168007bd25>).

3. Physical Lab Design

- **Dedicated Space:**
 - Separated pre-PCR (DNA extraction and library preparation) and post-PCR (DNA amplification and quality control) areas.
 - Unidirectional workflow to prevent possible cross-contamination.
 - From pre-PCR rooms to the post-PCR rooms. The daily workflow begins with work in the pre-PCR rooms and then moves to the post-PCR rooms. After finishing working in post-PCR rooms, do not return to the pre-PCR rooms.
 - From the Laboratory entering room to library preparation room. Start moving from the entry room, where you can change clothes, then move on to the changing area, where you can add protective clothing. Within the laboratory, do not move between rooms with different cleanliness levels (if you are working in the drilling room, do not enter the library preparation room and *vice versa*).
 - Separated rooms in the Laboratory
 - Entering room – for changing clothes, cataloguing and taking pictures, storage area.
 - Changing area – for dressing in clean suits, intermediate storage.
 - Main area – for general laboratory operations and equipment (including freezers/fridges).
 - Drilling rooms – for sampling and extraction.

- Library rooms – for extract purification, genomic library preparation.
- Clean room – for reagent preparation.
- **Environmental Controls:**
 - Laboratory air control
 - Positive air pressure – to prevent particles from entering the Laboratory from the outside air.
 - Particle counters – to check the conformity of the particle concentration in the air of the main area to the ISO standard (ISO 7).
 - Temperature – the reaction initiation temperatures depend on the general air temperature. The temperature should be set in consideration of the lowest temperature at which reactions start. A suitable working temperature is also important for the health of workers who wear protective clothing in the laboratory. The temperature of the Laboratory is between 20-22 °C.
 - Humidity – indoor humidity affects both indoor climate quality and human well-being. Problems with humidity can lead to mould, mildew, and dust mites, which can cause or worsen allergies and asthma. The normal humidity level for humans is between 40–60%.
 - Water supply
 - General water system – for Laboratory surfaces cleaning (adding bleach).
 - Separated cleaned ultra-pure water system (for example MilliQ system) – for lab protocols that do not require PCR grade water and for rinsing lab ware.
 - Cleaning and sterilization
 - Established protocols for laboratory cleaning:
 - Everyday cleaning – before starting and after finishing work, clean the used surfaces with decontaminants (bleach or special biodegradable agents) and remove trash. The Laboratory surfaces are resistant to chemicals that are used in experiments or during cleaning.
 - Weekly cleaning – clean surfaces, door handles, chairs and wash floors, remove trash.

- Monthly cleaning – clean flow hoods, surfaces, door handles, chairs, all possible places that may be touched during work and wash floors.
- Air sterilization with UV-light
 - Scheduled usage of UV lights in the laminar flow hoods.

- **Access Control:**

Access to the Laboratory should be limited only to trained personnel and maintenance staff who understand and follow the protocols for reducing potential contamination.

- Maintenance personnel who have received the necessary instructions
 - Necessary tools: if possible, then on-site in the Laboratory, but also possibility of cleaning specific tools that maintenance personnel need. Deep cleaning of the Laboratory after maintenance.
 - Planning maintenance at the beginning of the day to avoid possible contamination by maintenance personnel (so that they have not worked in the post-PCR laboratory before).
- Dressing in the Laboratory
 - Wearing outerwear is forbidden.
 - Before entering the changing area, change into comfortable, clean clothes.
 - In the changing area, add protective clothing (suit, hair net, mask, double gloves, lab boots, etc).

- **Specialized Equipment:**

- Laminar flow hoods with UV light and front air curtain (ISO standard 5 or less)
- Cross-linker for decontaminating consumables
- All other necessary equipment must be in the Laboratory so that there is no need to take samples out

4. Workflow and Protocols

The Laboratory workflow includes the following key components: 1) sample handling; 2) sampling and decontamination; 3) extraction (aDNA/proteins) and purification including storage of the extract; 4) genomic library preparation; 5) genomic library amplification and purification, quality assessment and sequencing.

- **Sample Handling:**

Sample handling includes receipt, documentation and storage of samples:

- Samples arrive at the Laboratory along with the Material Transfer Agreement that is signed by the sample provider and the head of the Laboratory (or PI of the project) according to the rules of involved institutions.
- Documentation of sample includes:
 - Assigning a Laboratory ID and entering the information about the sample in the Database (ID, project name, date of receipt, Laboratory person in charge, sample provider contact, and all the accompanying metadata of the sample).
 - Sample photographing and linking the pictures with the sample entry in the database (done in the entering room).
 - Transfer of the sample into a new bag in the changing area.
- During the data generation phase of the project, samples are stored in a dedicated Laboratory room, at a room temperature (20-25 °C). Samples are shipped back to the sample provider after the completion of the project if not specified otherwise in the Material Transfer Agreement.

- **Sampling and Decontamination:**

Sampling is done in the drilling room of the Laboratory under the hood and includes the following steps:

- Preparation of the decontamination station, flow hood and the necessary equipment
- Sampling

- Clean-up after each sample
- Final clean-up

Detailed protocol on sampling of tooth roots for ancient DNA can be found here: dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.6qpvrdr83gmk/v1

Decontamination of the sampled part of bioarchaeological material (e. g. tooth root or petrous bone core) is done in the drilling room and is aimed at reduction of surface contaminants prior to DNA extraction. Bleach and ethanol are used for decontaminating, and the process includes the following steps:

- Preparation of the decontamination station, flow hood and the necessary equipment
- Decontamination
- Drying sample
- Final clean-up

Detailed protocol on Decontamination of tooth roots/petrous bone cores for ancient DNA extraction can be found here: dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.eq2lynp4qvx9/v1

- **DNA extraction and extract purification:**

Extraction and purification of DNA are performed according to Dabney et al. (2013) PNAS (doi:10.1073/pnas.1314445110) with modifications (dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.n92ldzbpvx5b/v1 and dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.j8nlkwje6l5r/v1) and include:

- Preparation of the hood and necessary equipment in the drilling room
- Extraction (incubation with EDTA and Proteinase K for 72 hours)
- Final clean-up
- Preparation of the hood and necessary equipment in the library room
- Extract purification
- Final clean-up

Extracts are stored in tubes with low-binding inner surface and lid covered with Parafilm at -20 °C. Tubes are labelled according to the Laboratory standards. The location of the sample extract storage is linked with its Laboratory ID in the Laboratory Database.

- **Library preparation:**

DNA library preparation is performed in the library room. The primary protocol that is currently used follows double-stranded (ds) library preparation with no Uracil-DNA Glycosylase treatment (non-UDG) and with unique double indexing (UDI) for Illumina sequencing (dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.n2bvj6xqxlk5/v1). This protocol was optimized for ultra-short ancient DNA molecules, modified from Meyer & Kircher (2010) Cold Spring Harb. Protoc. (doi: 10.1101/pdb.prot5448). Library preparation consists of the following steps:

- Preparation of the flow hood and necessary equipment
- End repair
- Purification
- Adapter ligation
- Purification
- Adapter fill-in
- Preparation of the indexing PCR reaction mixes (each sample split into two reactions)
- Final clean-up

- **Indexing PCR, library purification, quantification and sequencing:**

All these steps are done at the modern DNA laboratory of the Core Facility of the Institute of Genomics of the University of Tartu.

Indexing PCR and purification of sequencing libraries is performed following the protocol (dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.rm7vzboy4vx1/v1), which was optimized for ultra-short ancient DNA molecules, modified from Meyer & Kircher (2010) Cold Spring Harb. Protoc. (doi: 10.1101/pdb.prot5448).

Quality and quantity of the dsDNA libraries are assessed by:

- Fluorometric quantitation (Qubit, Thermo Fisher Scientific)
- Parallel capillary electrophoresis (e. g., TapeStation, Agilent Technologies; Fragment Analyzer, Agilent Technologies)
- Quantitative PCR (QuantStudio5, Thermo Fisher Scientific; 7900HT Fast real-Time PCR Systems, Applied Biosystems)

DNA libraries are sequenced using the Illumina NextSeq 2000 instrument, usually using a 100-cycle kit in single-end mode, suitable for ancient DNA due to its fragmented state.

5. Personnel Training

To be granted access to the Laboratory, each new worker (irrespective of career stage, experience level or duration of stay) must first thoroughly read the “Guidelines for Ancient DNA Facility of the Institute of Genomics, University of Tartu” (attached as document titled UTIG_aDNA_Lab_Guidelines.pdf) and sign the Induction Form at the end of the document.

Irrespective of career stage or experience level, each new worker must go through the following stages of training before being allowed to work in the Laboratory independently:

1. Observing an experienced worker of the Laboratory perform in full the protocols the new worker is going to be using. This must be done at least once but can be repeated more times depending on the level of experience of the new worker. The decisions regarding repeating the process are made by the experienced worker.
2. Performing the protocols in full while being observed by the experienced worker. This must be done at least once but can be repeated more times depending on the level of experience of the new worker. The decisions regarding repeating the process are made by the experienced worker.

Students (BSc and MSc) and visitors are never allowed to work in the Laboratory without supervision.

6. Quality Assurance

- **Monitoring Contamination:**
 - Particle counters – readings are monitored to detect floating particle concentrations in the air that exceed the ISO standard thresholds (ISO 7 for the main Laboratory area).
 - Blank samples – to detect potential contamination in laboratory chemicals or between sample tubes.
 - Extraction blank – to trace potential contamination through extraction-purification and library preparation.
 - Library blank – to be able to distinguish between contaminated laboratory chemicals in the extraction-purification and library preparation steps.

- **Documentation:**

- All maintenance work in the Laboratory is recorded in the online calendar and in a designated notebook in the entering room with the contact information of the maintenance worker included.
- All Laboratory work is recorded in digital Laboratory Notebooks (e.g. Microsoft OneNote, Benchling), and each entry includes the following:
 - Workers – sometimes people work together (e. g. for training)
 - Protocols – specific versions of protocols are linked
 - Notes:
 - any deviations from the linked protocol
 - if new chemicals were taken into use (including new aliquots from joint-use containers)
 - any mistakes that happened
 - anything else of note
 - Laboratory Sheets – links to scans/photos of hand-filled tables with information that is recorded while inside the Laboratory:
 - comments on sample condition from drilling
 - sample weight
 - extraction buffer volumes
 - anything else that cannot be determined before entering the Laboratory

PS! Laboratory Sheets are not needed if tablets are used in the Laboratory, and the information can be entered directly into the Laboratory Book or Database.

7. Long-Term Maintenance and Updates

- **Infrastructure Maintenance:**

To ensure the functional operation of the Laboratory, the following systems/equipment should be checked regularly according to a defined procedure:

- Air filtration systems

- HEPA filters (general and flow hood filters) – to ensure air cleanliness.
- Calibrations of particle counters – to ensure the measurement accuracy of the equipment.
- Flow hoods – to verify compliance with the requirements set out in the standards and prevent sample contamination
- Clean water system maintenance – to ensure the system runs smoothly and water cleanliness is guaranteed
- Calibration of pipettes and balances – to ensure the measurement accuracy of the equipment

All these maintenances must be carried out by service providers or employees who have received the appropriate training for this purpose.

- **Policy Updates:**

- The maintenance instructions and frequency must be constantly updated according to the updated standards.
- If the maintenance is carried out by an employee, ensure that they complete additional training.
- If necessary, renew the amortized equipment to prevent disruption to Laboratory workflow.

8. Appendices and Resources

Contacts:

Manager of Ancient DNA Facilities: Lehti Saag (lehti.saag@ut.ee)

Senior Specialist of the Ancient DNA Laboratory: Helja Kabral (helja.kabral@ut.ee)

Head of the Archaeogenomics group of the Institute of Genomics, University of Tartu: Kristiina Tambets (kristiina.tambets@ut.ee)

Appendices:

UTIG_aDNA_Lab_Guidelines.pdf

Guidelines for Ancient DNA Facility of the Institute of Genomics, University of Tartu

General information

The following guidelines provide information for the use of cleanroom facilities (also called 'aDNA labs' further below in this document) in the University of Tartu Institute of Genomics (UT IG) building that are designed for the work on ancient human, animal, plant, and sediment DNA. The guidelines include information about health and safety aspects specific to the work within the facilities and rules for keeping the labs clean and contamination-free. Guidance is provided for best practices for the shared use of equipment and storage space, supply of reagents, and waste management. For any questions about the use of the labs, please refer to the following key contacts for further information:

Name	Role	Phone	e-mail
	Manager of Ancient DNA Facility, Ancient DNA Research Fellow		
	Training lead, aDNA lab senior specialist		
	Deputy Director in charge of the Estonian Biocentre, Professor of Archaeogenomics		
	Director of Institute of Genomics, Professor of Evolutionary Genomics		
	Emergency and accidents		
	First Aid Responder		

Dial 0 to get to an outside phone line.

Location of the facilities: Institute of Genomics, Riia 23b, Tartu 51010. Cleanrooms in the basement (Floor 0) are key card access only and must be entered from the last door in the UT IG building, down the stairs immediately to the left.

NB! IMPORTANT! Do NOT ENTER the cleanrooms if you have already been **working in a POST-PCR lab the same day, as we do not want amplified PCR products entering the clean rooms.**

To get your key and card activated for access, please contact Merilin Raud. All new users must confirm that they have read and understood these guidelines, go through the Health and Safety and Lab Induction, and sign both forms.

Basic principles of workflow

The cleanroom facilities are hosted by the University of Tartu Institute of Genomics (UT IG), and anyone working in the labs has to comply with the general rules of laboratory use in the premises of the UT IG as outlined on the university website. Also, while working in the facilities, you will have to follow the specific rules of our ancient DNA lab so as not to compromise your work and that of others sharing the lab. The rules to minimize contamination and to keep the labs clean and well-maintained are essential for maintaining high standards of research in the labs. It is of utmost importance that these guidelines are followed and that any deviation is reported to your PI and a Facilities Manager immediately to find ways to minimize the effect of the deviation and to correct it. In case of an emergency or accident, make sure the incident is reported to the Facilities Manager and your PI. All incidents should be reported, including 'near misses'.

The following guidelines are structured by the following four themes:

1. Guidelines of specific aspects of health and safety in the aDNA labs.
2. Guidelines to minimize contamination risks and secure the authenticity of results.
3. Guidelines to keep the labs well stocked with reagents.
4. Guidelines for keeping equipment well maintained and in working order.

All users of the cleanrooms must read these guidelines carefully and go through both (i) health and safety and (ii) lab inductions to get access to the labs. In the lab induction form, all new users have to confirm that they have read the guidelines for working in the cleanroom facilities and agree to the rules of the lab use. In case you are uncertain about any aspects of the protocol you are following or the facilities in general, please ask for extra guidance either from your supervisor, training lead, or facilities manager.

aDNA lab user meetings will be held at regular intervals, and all lab users are expected to participate unless traveling abroad. Please ask your supervisor about the schedule of these meetings and ask your name to be added to the relevant mailing list.

Guidelines of specific aspects of health and safety in the aDNA labs

All basic health and safety rules that apply to other labs in the UT IG also apply to the aDNA labs. In the event of an emergency that requires the **Emergency Services (e.g., fire, serious accident)**, Dial **112**. There is a telephone that you can use in the main area of the cleanroom.

SOME BASIC RULES

- Eating and drinking are not allowed inside the clean area.
- Never apply cosmetics in the laboratory.
- Use appropriate care with electrical equipment and sharp objects.
- Do not use equipment (autoclave, UV cross-linker, etc.) unless you have been trained in its use.
- Visitors unauthorized by your PI and supervisor should be kept out of the labs (do not take friends or visitors into the labs without relevant coordination).
- Make sure you are familiar with how to use the equipment before using it.
- Make sure you keep the equipment and rooms clean all the time.
- Make sure you are aware of the risks associated with the chemicals you use.
- If you are feeling ill, please stay home – it is not worth injuring yourself in the lab or spreading sickness to your colleagues.

WORKING WITH CHEMICALS

In the aDNA labs, there are several chemicals that are hazardous to health. Do not use them without training. Below is a short guidance on some of these chemicals, what they are, and how to deal with them. Some of the chemicals listed are not currently stored in our aDNA labs, but since other aDNA labs may use them, it is helpful to be aware of these as well. If you are unsure about anything related to chemicals, ask your supervisor for guidance.

- **Sodium Hypochlorite (NaOCl) or bleach** is corrosive, so be cautious when using and avoid any contact of the chemical with your skin. In case of contact with skin, wash immediately at the sink with plenty of water. If symptoms develop, obtain immediate medical attention.
- **Guanidinium HCl**: Many buffers in the lab contain guanidine salts such as Gu-HCl (e.g., Qiagen PB, ATL, and others). If these come into contact with **bleach**, they form **toxic chlorine gas**. If you need to **bleach** something that has contained these liquids or wipe up a DNA spill with such liquids, always first clean with WATER and/or ETHANOL. Only after the guanidinium salt is cleaned up first can you then **bleach** the implement/surface. Remember to clean with ETHANOL afterward to avoid bleaching of cloths, more chlorine gas formation, skin irritation, etc.
- [not used] **Guanidinium thiocyanate** is used in some of the silica extraction methods (e.g., Qiagen buffer AL and others). When in contact with **acids** or **bleach**, extremely **toxic hydrogen cyanide gas (HCN)** may be released, which **can be fatal**. If you spill this reagent, **DO NOT** bring it into contact with **acids** or **bleach**. Always wipe up guanidine thiocyanate with dry paper towels first, followed by clean WATER and then ETHANOL.

- [not used] **Phenol** is highly toxic. It penetrates latex gloves and can be lethal if spilled on the skin. Never use phenol without proper training. Always know what to do about a spill, whether on you or as a leaking tube. NEVER leave a spill unattended. Always use in a vented hood. If possible, centrifuge phenol at a time when few people are in the lab because vapors are released even in “sealed” tubes.
- [not used] **Hydrochloride acid** is highly corrosive, even when diluted. Never use outside a flow hood.

Always add acid to WATER and not the reverse. [acid => H₂O]

Always store **acid** bottles on the bottom shelves of the chemical cupboard.

Always wear eye protection when working with bleach. If you get **bleach** spills into the eye, immediately eyewash at the eyewash station (main lab room above the sink). Speed is essential, IMMEDIATELY irrigate with neutralising eyewash solution followed by eyewash solution or clean water, holding the eyelids apart for at least 10 minutes. **Obtain immediate medical attention.**

When working with any of the chemicals mentioned above, make sure you know exactly where the relevant waste should go.

WASTE MANAGEMENT

Some chemical waste is produced in large scale, e.g., Qiagen buffer products, and are therefore collected in 5 L or 20 L plastic containers that are marked with the containers' contents.

- Never mix buffer wastes in a single bottle, but use separate bottles for **acids**, solvents (e.g., phenol), or Qiagen extraction buffers.
- Use separate bottles for **acids**, **bases**, organic solvents, and other extraction/purification buffers.
- **Always label** the bottles/containers properly with contents, date, and your name so we know what it is.

WORKING ALONE IN THE LAB

There should be no use of the facilities out of hours unless permission is granted by your supervisor. Lab users should also be aware of the risks associated with working alone and take appropriate steps to control them. Make sure someone with access to the lab (normally your supervisor) knows when you are working alone, and let them know when you finish and are out of the lab facilities.

Guidelines to minimize contamination risks and to secure the authenticity of results

SOME BASIC RULES

- Make sure you carefully follow the routine details specified for entry into the labs.
- Do not bring items unrelated to your work to the labs.
- Do not bring your lab book or laptop into the clean labs.
- All new items and equipment that need to be brought into the labs should be carefully decontaminated first.
- Keep freezers tidy. Only pellets, extracts and reagents can be stored permanently.
- Any intermediate-stage products of your work can be stored only short term.
- If you have any ideas on how to improve these guidelines or to change lab practices in general, please share them with a facilities manager.

HOW TO ENTER THE CLEAN LAB

Before entering the aDNA facility, **make sure that you have not been to any modern DNA labs or post-PCR genomic labs that day**, and that you have a clean set of clothes, i.e., clothes that have not seen the modern labs since the last washing and are kept in the aDNA lab. If you absolutely must go into the clean lab after having been to the modern labs, you need to take a shower first, as PCR products can be in your hair and on your skin. There is a shower on the 6th floor of the UT IG building in the sauna room. You must bring your own towel and check availability, as this room is often rented out for meetings/events.

The UT IG aDNA lab consists of 5 major areas, in the order of cleanliness: purification/library preparation rooms, drill/extraction rooms, main lab, changing room, entry room. The entry room is outside of the technical cleanroom zone.

Leave any winter coats and/or boots outside the lab in available lockers or hooks.

Entry room

1. Any new deliveries should be placed on the table immediately to the left.
2. The area to the right containing a shoe rack and hooks is for your inside shoes and clothes only. Please change into a pair of clean clogs.
3. If you have long hair, please tie it back.
4. Change into your lab clothes.

Changing room

1. If you need to bring your cell phone into the lab, put it into a designated mini grip bag from your right without putting the phone down anywhere before. Place the bag containing the phone on the edge of the table on your right.
2. Put on gloves from the glove rack to your left.
3. If you brought a cell phone, clean the bag you put it in thoroughly with DNA remover (e.g. DNA Exitus) and place it a bit further from the edge of the table. Do not open the bag once inside the lab.

4. If you do not yet have lab boots, put blue covers over your clogs.
5. Put on a hair net. Make sure your hair is inside the net.
6. Put on a facemask.
7. Put on a (clean) suit, making sure not to drag your sleeves on the ground when you step into it.
8. Put on protective eyewear.
9. Check in the mirror that all hairs are under the net and the facemask is properly adjusted.
10. Put on lab boots if you have them, stepping into the area behind the line on the floor.
11. Put on a second pair of gloves from the glove rack next to the main room door. This pair is the only one you can change inside the lab.
12. Now, you may enter the main room.

Once you are suited up, do not go back outside to the entry room wearing your suit.

When leaving the clean lab

1. Remove your outer gloves. Place these in the trash.
2. Remove your eyewear and place it either on your hanger or in the “dirty” box.
3. Take off your suit and place on your hanger. If it is dirty or worn, place it in the trash.
4. Remove the hairnet and facemask and place on your hanger. If dirty or used for over a week, place in the trash. Please do not take down tied hair or ‘fluff’ your hair until you are well outside the lab area.
5. If you had your phone with you in the lab, remove it from the bag and put the bag away, making sure not to touch any surfaces with the phone.
6. Exit to the entry room, remove your inner gloves (and shoe covers) and wash your hands in the sink.

ANTI-CONTAMINATION GUIDELINES

NB! DO NOT ENTER THE CLEAN LAB AFTER HAVING BEEN IN A POST-PCR LAB.

- Do not bring anything from the modern lab into the clean lab (this includes lab books, reagents, gel images, pens, computers, etc.)
- Always be conscious about what you touch with your hands – if you touch your face/hair you must change gloves.
- Always wipe all work surfaces (and chairs) with DNA-remover (e.g. DNA Exitus).
- Only store liquid wastes in the cupboard designated for waste. Bring full waste containers to the chemical storage room when leaving the labs.
- Always keep doors closed, i.e., do not work in the drill/extraction or purification/library preparation room with the door open.

NB! IMPORTANT! DO NOT USE THE THERMOCYCLERS FOR PCR.

CLEANING

To minimize contamination, it is **absolutely crucial that the clean labs are kept clean**. To ensure this, every user is expected to clean their workspace after they are finished in the lab (see everyday cleaning). In addition, each active user will be assigned to a weekly and monthly cleaning rotation. The weekly cleaning will be done in teams of two or three and must be done every single week - even if the labs look clean. The weekly/monthly cleaning rota is posted on the door to the clean labs as well as inside the labs. Use the checklists as you are cleaning and return them to the folder by the door of the changing room. If you can't clean when it's your turn, **you are responsible for finding a replacement**. Not cleaning the labs or finding a replacement will have consequences. If you do not assist in these communal duties, other busy people have to step in. If you think you should not be on the rota, let a facilities manager know.

Everyday cleaning

Every user must clean their work area after they finish their daily work in the lab. This includes:

- Emptying the table bins and the bins on the floor.
- Washing all surfaces with DNA remover (e.g. DNA Exitus).
- Cleaning equipment after use (this includes drills, drill bits, centrifuges, etc.)
- In the main room, there are two blue buckets for cleaning racks, etc.
 - Fill the bleach bucket with lukewarm water (not hot) and pour in some bleach (wear safety goggles) in a roughly 1 to 25 volume ratio.
 - Fill the “soap and water only” bucket with water.
 - Soak racks, etc., in the bleach water for at least 5 minutes, rinse in the water bucket, and allow to dry on the dish drying rack.
 - When finished, pour out the bleach dilution, follow with water from the water bucket, and rinse both down with normal tap water. Leave the buckets upside-down in the sink to dry.
- To clean goggles, fill the “soap and water only” bucket with warm water and add some dish soap. Wash the goggles in the soapy water, rinse them, and let them dry on paper towels. Replace into the “clean goggles” box in the changing room.

Weekly cleaning

- Wipe all handles (of freezers/fridges, cupboards, doors, faucets) with DNA remover (e.g. DNA Exitus).
- Sweep the floors.
- Empty all the bins.
- Move cardboard boxes to the 1st floor for pick up.
- Take out waste bags to the outside bin for pick up.
- Take any full waste bottles to the entrance room and inform a facilities manager that they are ready for pick-up.
- Check stock supplies, re-stock the extraction/library preparation area shelves if needed and let the senior lab specialist know if the entry room needs re-stocking.
- Use the cleaning form, check off the parts you have completed, and leave it in the folder in the changing room.

Monthly cleaning

- Wipe all handles and surfaces (freezers/fridges, cupboards, table tops, hoods, doors, faucets) with DNA remover (e.g. DNA Exitus).
- Sweep and wash the floor with a diluted solution of bleach.
- Empty all the bins.
- Move cardboard boxes to the 1st floor for pick up.
- Take out waste bags to the outside bin for pick up.
- Take any full waste bottles to the entrance room and inform a facilities manager that they are ready for pick-up.
- Check stock supplies, re-stock the extraction/library preparation area shelves if needed and let the senior lab specialist know if the entry room needs re-stocking.
- Use the cleaning form, check off the parts you have completed, and leave it in the folder in the changing room.

AVOIDING CONTAMINATION WHILE WORKING IN THE LAB

- Always make aliquots. Never pipette a liquid from a communal stock bottle.
- Never over-fill tubes.
- Always wipe up spills immediately. First with water, then DNA remover (e.g. DNA Exitus) if a spill is of DNA sample.
- Do not leave the lids off of pipette tip boxes.
- Always use DNA remover (e.g. DNA Exitus) on all your benches and centrifuges after use.
- Always wipe down the inside of the flow hoods.
- Always empty waste bags that are full or nearly full.

Guidelines to keep the labs well stocked with reagents

STOCKS

- Do not use anything that has someone else's name on it unless you have explicit permission.
- Before leaving the lab for the day, re-stock the extraction/library preparation area shelves if you took something from these and let the senior lab specialist know if the entry room needs re-stocking.
- If you take the second to last (or last) reagent tube from any stock in the freezer, let the senior lab specialist know.
- If you need to use a lot of any supply, please ask the senior lab specialist to order it in advance (e.g., Qiagen kits, Amicon filters, scalpels, Minelute columns, etc.).
- Storage space in freezers and cabinets is limited, so be considerate and clean out your drawers regularly.
- Whenever you open a common stock (e.g., a water bottle), always write the date of opening on the bottle.
- Do not leave empty boxes in the clean lab area, even if they are not yours.

Guidelines for keeping equipment well maintained and in working order

EQUIPMENT

General guidance: If you think something is broken in the lab, put a post-it note on the machine/item and inform the facilities manager.

Centrifuges

- Always balance centrifuges
- Always use lids on the centrifuges, clean them after use, and leave lids open.
- Remove broken tubes/parts of tubes from centrifuges immediately – the pieces can break your tubes or other lab users' tubes.
- Check rotors for cleanliness and soak inserts in diluted bleach with other cleaning as necessary.

Pipettes

- Never pipette a volume outside the range of a pipette (e.g., a P20 pipette does not go above 20 μ l). If you use it for 24 μ l, you will de-calibrate it and cause mechanical and measuring problems. The appropriate range is written on all pipettes.
- Inform the facilities manager of any inaccurate or not working pipettes.

Thermocyclers

- **NB! ONLY USED FOR INCUBATION AT CERTAIN TEMPERATURES NOT PCR.**
 - PCR and amplification of libraries should be performed in separate lab facilities designed for modern DNA, e.g., those upstairs on the 3rd floor.

CLEAN-LAB BOOKING

Always book lab time using the online Gmail calendars (to be shared with you). Book the specific space you need and specify your name and what you will be doing (extractions, building libraries, etc.) in the event title.

- Only schedule the amount of time you actually need and **be on time**.
- Finish your work and clean the bench within your allotted time.
- If you have to change a booking or cannot use the time you have booked in the lab, make sure to change it and **inform people through the designated Slack channel**.

Estonian Biocentre Institute of Genomics aDNA Lab Induction Form

Name of the new user/guest: _____,

e-mail: _____

I confirm that I have read the Guidelines for working in the Ancient DNA Facilities of the Institute of Genomics, University of Tartu and agree to comply with them in order to conduct my work in the labs according to these guidelines. I am familiar with the risks associated with and related to the protocols I will be using in the lab, and I understand that health and safety are my responsibility. I understand that my supervisor and the Facilities Manager are available for advice and can prohibit access to the labs in case of any activity that does not comply with these guidelines or good laboratory practice.

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Lab Health and Safety/General Procedures Induction completed by:

Name: _____

Date: _____

As the PI supporting the work of the new user/guest in the cleanrooms, I can confirm that there are sufficient funds to cover the costs related to the project they are undertaking.

PI name: _____

Signature: _____

Supervisor/host:

I, the undersigned, hereby acknowledge that I have introduced my guest to our laboratory practices and protocols to be used in the Ancient DNA Facilities of the Institute of Genomics, University of Tartu and that I will provide an adequate level of supervision and I am responsible for their behavior in the labs for the duration of their stay.

Name: _____

Date: _____

Signature: _____